

**ENSURING REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH OF WOMEN AND ANALYSIS OF
NEGATIVE EFFECTS ON THEIR BLOOD AND CIRCULATORY SYSTEM. (IN THE
EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAGISTAN)**

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Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to quality education and upbringing of women. In the words of Abdurauf Fitrat, the great exponent of Jadidism, "*Mothers are educators of all humanity.*" Indeed, women are a great link that ensures the future of the society. But, first of all, it is important to provide the society with a healthy generation, along with a healthy mind. It is no secret that the birth of a healthy offspring largely depends on the health of mothers. Therefore, a number of positive reforms are being carried out in our country today, including in many fields, including biology and medicine. As a result of the reforms, in recent years, fundamental improvement of the health care system, provision of quality medical services to the public, further strengthening of the reproductive health of the population, protection of motherhood and childhood, and creation of necessary conditions for the upbringing of a healthy generation have been defined as one of the priority directions of state policy.

Especially, the health of women of reproductive age in the Republic is one of the topical issues today. In recent years, a number of decisions on the same issue have been announced by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their implementation is being ensured. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4513 of November 8, 2019 "On improving the quality and further expanding the scope of medical care provided to women of reproductive age, pregnant women and children" is one of these¹.

One of the issues stated in this decision and the most important one is related to the health protection of women and girls of reproductive age living in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and the further improvement of the quality of the provided medical care. Today, the population living in this area suffers the most from environmental damage. As a result, the number of people suffering from various hereditary diseases is increasing among the population

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of the region. It is known that many diseases of the genetic apparatus are inextricably linked with blood. When the blood composition of the population living in Karakalpakstan is analyzed, it can be found that the amount of platelets in the blood of overweight people has decreased. As a result, the amount of blood clotting decreases. If we dwell on the causes of the condition, the factors of a decrease in platelets in the blood are as follows:

(thrombocytopenia - less than 180×10^9 cells/l)

- Congenital blood diseases (hemophilia);
- Idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenic purpura;
- Systemic lupus erythematosus;
- Infection (viral and bacterial infections, malaria, toxoplasmosis);
- Aplastic anemia;
- Paroxysmal evening hemoglobinuria;
- Evans syndrome (autoimmune hemolytic anemia and thrombocytopenia);
- Blood transfusion;
- Premature birth in children;
- Heart failure;
- Thrombosis of renal veins.

It can be observed that the majority of the population of the region has an increased level of leukocytes in the blood. One of the main reasons for the increase of these white blood cells is that the body does not get enough vitamins. Children born to mothers suffering from chronic anemia during irregular pregnancy are more likely to develop white blood cell disease. This disease is usually hidden and manifests itself when a person reaches adolescence and the body begins to mature. At the same time, all human organs require proper nutrition, and hormonal changes begin to occur in the body.

The frequent occurrence of pathologies related to the blood and circulatory system, as above, in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is directly related to the conditions of the country. As a result of the unstable ecological situation, the reduction of green areas, the

death of crops as a result of salt dust storms, and the reduction of fruits, vegetables, and greens in the diet of the population hurt human health and its immune system. Today, the restoration of the health of the population in the country imposes responsible tasks on biological science in many ways. That is, the creation of plant varieties that are suitable for the ecology of the region will help to ease the tension in the country, even a little, and improve the health of the population.

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